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Background

The Accelerated Testing Methodology (ATM) can be used for the prediction of the long-term life of CFRP.

The tensile strength of unidirectional CFRP is important and fundamental data for the reliable design of CFRP structures.

Recently, thermoplastic epoxy resin (TPEP) has been developed and used for CFRP structures.

Objective

In this study, the statistical life of TPEP resin impregnated carbon fiber strand (CFRTP strand) under fatigue tension loading was evaluated under dry and wet conditions using the ATM we developed.

Formulation of statistical fatigue strength

$$\log \sigma_f = \log \sigma_0 + \frac{1}{\alpha} \log[-\ln(1 - P_f)] + n_R \log \left[\frac{E_f(t, T)}{E_f(t_0, T_0)} \right] - F_f[\log(2N_f)]$$

Strength reduction caused by viscoelasticity

$$\log \sigma_f^* = \log \sigma_0(t_0, T_0) + \frac{1}{\alpha} \log[-\ln(1 - P_f)] + n_R \log \left[\frac{E_f(t, T)}{E_f(t_0, T_0)} \right]$$

Strength reduction caused by the number of load cycles

$$\log S_f = \log \frac{\sigma_f}{\sigma_0} - n_R \log \left[\frac{E_f(t, T)}{E_f(t_0, T_0)} \right] = \frac{1}{\alpha} \log[-\ln(1 - P_f)] - F_f[\log(2N_f)]$$

- t : Failure time
- t_0 : Reference time
- T : Temperature
- T_0 : Reference temperature
- P_f : Failure probability
- f : Frequency
- N_f : Number of cycles to failure
- σ_0 and α : Scale and shape parameters of static strength at t_0 and T_0
- n_R : Viscoelastic parameter determined by failure mode
- E_f : Viscoelastic modulus of matrix resin under cyclic loading
- F_f : Fatigue degradation parameter

Testing method

Test material

CFRTP strand	Carbon fiber	Resin
T700/TPEP	T700SC-6000	Thermoplastic epoxy (TPEP)
T300/TPEP	T300-3000	

Viscoelastic test for matrix resin

Static strength test for CFRTP strands

Fatigue strength test for CFRTP strands

E : Relaxation modulus of matrix resin

σ_0 : Scale parameters of static strength at t_0 and T_0

α : Shape parameters of static strength at t_0 and T_0

n_R : Viscoelastic parameter determined by failure mode

F_f : Fatigue degradation parameter

Results and Discussion

Master curve of relaxation modulus for TPEP neat resin

Parameters in Formulae

		σ_0 [MPa]	α [-]	n_R [-]
T700/TPEP	Dry	4970	15	0.102
	Wet	4710	23	0.167
T300/TPEP	Dry	3600	16	0.060
	Wet	3570	20	0.127

Strength reduction caused by viscoelasticity

Prediction of tensile fatigue strength

Fatigue tensile strength versus number of cycles to failure

Strength reduction caused by the number of load cycles

Comparison of T700/TPEP and T300/TPEP

Conclusion

- Statistical fatigue strength of unidirectional CFRTP under tensile loading in the fiber direction can be predicted using ATM not only in dry but also in wet conditions.
- Fatigue strength σ_f is affected by fiber strength and water absorption.
- Strength reduction caused by viscoelasticity of matrix resin σ_f^* is negligibly small.
- Strength reduction caused by the number of load cycles S_f is very large.
- The behavior of S_f is affected by carbon fibers.

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